

Sponge bioerosion on reef-building corals: dependent on the environment or on skeletal density?

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Key words: Calcification rate, coral reefs, *Montastraea annularis*, *Porites astreoides*, ocean warming, ocean acidification.

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3 **Abstract** X-radiographic techniques were used to measure the skeletal density and percentage of bioerosion
4 in *Montastraea annularis* and *Porites astreoides* growing in reefs subjected to suboptimal (Veracruz Reef
5 System, VRS) and optimal (Mahahual, MH) environmental conditions for coral reef development. Skeletal
6 density was higher in *P. astreoides* than in *M. annularis* and was higher in corals from MH than from the
7 VRS. The percentage of the skeleton excavated by boring sponges was significantly correlated with skeletal
8 density. These results are the first contribution that seeks to understand the interactions of the environment
9 and coral skeletal density on sponge bioerosion and suggest that bioerosion is linked to coral skeletal density
10 rather than to environmental conditions. Finally, based on the differences in growth strategies between the
11 two species, the effects of climate change on sponge bioerosion rates could have repercussions on coral reef
12 biodiversity and community structure.
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Introduction

The reef framework is the basis of the huge biological diversity associated with coral reefs, damping wave energy as well as generating a variety of ecological phenomena (Sutton 1983; Choat and Bellwood 1991; Done et al. 1996; Moberg and Folke 1999). Although a diversity of organisms builds reefs, corals provide the main reef structure, producing large amounts of calcium carbonate substratum, which offsets the erosion of the reef, resulting in net CaCO_3 accumulation rates (Wild et al. 2007).

Destructive physical, chemical and biological processes are also important in determining the net CaCO_3 accumulation rates. Physical disturbance, associated with severe storms and cyclones, is an important episodic process that influences reef framework development, largely through the generation of coral rubble, the deposition of which is an important reef-building process in its own right (Hubbard 1997; Blanchon and Jones 1997; Rasser and Riegl 2002). A wide range of reef-associated fauna facilitates bioerosion, including fish and echinoid taxa, as well as endolithic forms of cyanobacteria, chlorophytes, fungi, sponges, bivalves and worms (Spencer 1992; Glynn 1997; Edinger 2000; Perry and Hepburn 2008). These biological agents of destruction play two key roles in reefs: (1) they directly degrade the primary and secondary framework, increasing susceptibility to physical and chemical erosion and thus strongly influence carbonate budgets (Goreau and Hartman 1963; Frydl and Stearn 1978; Bak 1994), and (2) they may produce large amounts of sediment (Neumann 1966; Gygi 1975; Moore and Shedd 1977). Among boring organisms, sponges are usually the dominant group around the world (MacGeachy and Stearn 1976; Hudson 1977).

Coral skeletal density depends on how the calcareous material is used by the coral to construct the skeleton (Carricart-Ganivet and Merino 2001; Carricart-Ganivet 2011). Changes in this parameter have been attributed to differences in sedimentation rates and sea surface temperatures (Lough and Barnes 2000; Carricart-Ganivet and Merino 2001; Carricart-Ganivet 2004). On the other hand, it has been reported that bioerosion increases when environmental conditions are suboptimal for the development of the coral reef framework (Goreau and Hartman 1963; Carballo et al. 1994; Holmes 1997, 2000; Holmes et al. 2000, Holmes et al. 2009).

Montastraea annularis is a major reef-building coral in the West Atlantic Ocean

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3 (Goreau 1959) and coral assemblages in the region were once dominated by this species
4 (Alvarez-Filip et al. 2009). On the other hand, due to climate change, *Porites astreoides*
5 has become a more prominent component of coral reef communities throughout the
6 Caribbean (Yakob and Mumby 2011). *Porites astreoides* constructs denser skeletons than
7 *M. annularis*, and both species have denser skeletons in warmer waters than in cold
8 waters in the western Atlantic (Carricart-Ganivet 2004; Elizalde-Rendón et al. 2010).
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14 This study aims to quantify bioerosion by macro-borers, especially sponges, in *M.*
15 *annularis* and *P. astreoides* growing in reefs subjected to different sea surface
16 temperatures and degrees of continental influence in the Mexican Atlantic. In addition,
17 the study aims to test if sponge bioerosion varies according to coral skeletal density or to
18 environmental conditions.
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24 **Material and methods**

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26 For this study, two reef systems with different environmental conditions were
27 selected (Fig. 1). The Veracruz Reef System (VRS) is located in the Southern Gulf of
28 Mexico off Veracruz City, the most important and biggest cargo port in Mexico (19° 03' –
29 19° 12' N; 95° 56' – 96° 04' W). Annual sea surface temperature (SST) averages 26.6°C in
30 the VRS with temperatures as low as 16.0°C in the winter (Secretaría de Marina 1978;
31 Carrillo et al. 2007). River run-off, mainly due to the discharge from the Jamapa-Atoyac
32 Rivers, demographic growth, and increasing anthropogenic impact due to major port
33 activities such as oil spills and other chemical pollutants, overfishing, unrestricted
34 recreational diving, ship groundings, sewage effluents, dredging, and boat anchoring, have
35 generated turbid and high nutrient-enriched water conditions in the VRS (Horta-Puga and
36 Carricart-Ganivet 1990; Cruz-Piñón et al. 2003; Horta-Puga 2003, 2007). Mahahual Reef
37 (MH; 18°43'N; 87°41'W) is a fringing reef that occurs on the south-east coast of the
38 Yucatán Peninsula and is part of the Mesoamerican Barrier Reef System (MBRS), which
39 flanks the east coast of the peninsula, from Isla Contoy in the north to the Gulf of Honduras
40 in the south. The average annual SST in MH is 28.2°C, ranging from 29.7°C in the summer
41 to 26.5°C in the winter (Carricart-Ganivet 2004). Since the peninsula has a karstic nature,
42 the lack of soils causes rapid rainwater percolation down to the water table and there is no
43 surface river run-off to the sea (Ward et al. 1985; Merino et al. 1990). Therefore,
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3 continental influences on these reefs are low even though they are very close to the coast,
4 resulting in high water transparency with low nutrients levels and low sedimentation rates
5 (Jordan-Dahlgren and Rodríguez-Martínez 2003; Cruz-Piñón et al. 2003).
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9 Eleven colonies of *M. annularis* were collected in Isla de Sacrificios reef in the VRS
10 and 10 colonies in MH. In the VRS, nine colonies of *P. astreoides* were collected, five from
11 Isla Verde reef and four from Pájaros reef. Seven colonies of *P. astreoides* were collected
12 in MH. Colonies were collected in the VRS in July 2007 and in MH in September 2007. All
13 colonies had a healthy aspect, ranged between 15 and 20 cm in height, and were growing at
14 depths ranging from 2 to 5 m.
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19 From each colony, an ~7 mm thick slice was removed from the vertical plane close
20 to the center, following the main growth axis, using a rock saw equipped with a diamond-
21 tipped blade. All slices were rinsed with freshwater, dried at 80°C in a laboratory oven, and
22 X-radiographed using 240 × 300 mm Kodak® MIN-R 2000 mammography film in a
23 conventional CGR X-ray machine. Exposures were 50 kVp, 100 mA, 5 mAs, with a
24 1.80 m focal length. These conditions allowed the highest contrast and the most accurate
25 image reproduction as reported by Guillaume (1994). Each X-radiograph was taken in the
26 presence of an aluminum bar, placed along the anode-cathode axis of the X-ray machine
27 to correct for the heel effect, and an aragonitic step-wedge, built of blocks cut from
28 the shell of a giant clam *Tridacna maxima* (see Carricart-Ganivet and Barnes 2007).
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37 Developed X-ray films were digitized with a ScanMaker 9800XL, using a TMA
38 1600 lid for transparent films (MICROTEK, Inc.; <http://www.microtek.com>). Using the
39 methods of Carricart-Ganivet and Barnes (2007), the digitized images of the X-radiographs
40 were used to measure density (g cm^{-3}) along a track placed on the vertical growth axis
41 observed in the digital contact print of each slice using ImageJ 1.41 free software
42 (<http://rsbweb.nih.gov/ij/>). The thickness of each coral slice was measured at 10 mm
43 intervals with a set of calipers (0.01 mm precision) along the same track on which density
44 was measured on the digitized X-radiograph and intermediate thicknesses were interpolated
45 by linear regressions between the intervals (see Carricart-Ganivet and Barnes 2007). A data
46 series of absolute density vs. distance was generated for each track, and mean skeletal
47 density was calculated for each colony slice.
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56 The characteristic patterns of skeletal excavation by four macro-borer groups:
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3 sponges, polychaetes, sipunculids, and the bivalve *Lithophaga* spp., were identified on each
4 digitized X-ray film (Hein and Risk 1975; Highsmith 1981a; Highsmith et al. 1983;
5 Hutchings 1986). Using ImageJ 1.41 free software, the total area of each slice, total
6 bioeroded area and eroded area bored by each group were calculated for each coral slice.
7 Then, the percentages of total bioerosion and of bioerosion by each group were obtained.
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13 **Results and discussion**

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16 Mean skeletal density and the percentage of bioerosion caused by each of the four
17 macro-boring groups: sponges, polychaetes, *Lithophaga* and sipunculans, as well as the
18 total percentage of bioerosion found in skeletons of *Montastraea annularis*, and *Porites*
19 *astreoides* growing in MH and in the VRS are given in Table 1. In accordance with
20 previous observations (Carricart-Ganivet 2004; Elizalde-Rendón et al. 2010), density was
21 significantly higher in *P. astreoides* than in *M. annularis* (*t*-test for independent samples; *P*
22 = 0.001). On the other hand, density was significantly higher in *P. astreoides* from MH
23 when compared to the VRS (*t*-test for independent samples; *P* = 0.02). Although the
24 skeletal density of *M. annularis* was higher in slices obtained from MH compared to those
25 taken from the VRS, there was no significant difference found (*t*-test for independent
26 samples; *P* = 0.22).
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35 One would expect that the less dense skeleton would be more easily burrowed by
36 bioeroders. Nonetheless, the results indicate an increase in the percentage of total
37 bioerosion as skeletal density increases (Fig. 2). Highsmith (1981a) suggested that this
38 counterintuitive result could be explained considering that bioeroders depend on protection
39 from the substrate they have penetrated. Relatively dense coral skeletons are more resistant
40 to erosion by the scraping or grazing by fishes and sea urchins, which are known to break
41 off pieces of coral with their powerful jaws and eat the boring and infaunal organisms thus
42 exposed (Randall 1967, 1974; Glynn et al. 1972). Therefore, denser corals, such as *P.*
43 *astreoides*, with dense outer layers probably offer borers greater protection from powerful
44 predatory fishes and urchins than corals with less dense skeletons (Highsmith 1981a). This
45 is supported by the fact that the percentage of total bioerosion is positively related to
46 skeletal density when the results from this study are pooled with those reported by other
47 authors for different species and localities (Fig. 3).
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3 In this study, in all cases, the most important bioeroders were boring sponges. They
4 accounted for 79 to 94% of total bioerosion in *M. annularis*, and for 74 to 90% in *P.*
5 *astreoides* (Table 2). Furthermore, a high significantly positive relationship was observed
6 between the percentage of bioerosion caused by sponges and skeletal density (Fig. 4), a
7 pattern similar to that reported by Highsmith (1981b) and Schönberg (2002). The
8 remaining borers in both coral species in order of importance were *Lithophaga* spp.,
9 polychaetes and sipunculans (Table 2). The fact that sponges were clearly the most
10 important borers in all cases is because they hollow out an extensive system of cavities and
11 tunnels in the coral skeleton where they that eventually undermine the entire periphery of
12 the dead parts of the coral head. In contrast, bivalves, sipunculans, and polychaetes remove
13 only a relatively small volume of coral skeleton (Highsmith et al. 1983).

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15 On the other hand, Schönberg (2002) pointed out that it might be important to
16 now how sponge bioerosion may be related to skeletal density and how it may change
17 depending on environmental conditions. Rose and Risk (1985) suggested that in areas of
18 stressed reefs erosion rates would increase, since suboptimal environmental conditions for
19 reef-building corals, such as increased nutrient levels, freshwater influx, elevated
20 sedimentation rates and turbidity may enhance sponge bioerosion (Goreau and Hartman
21 1963; Carballo et al. 1994; Holmes 1997). However, although some studies show that
22 bioeroding sponges become more abundant and diverse with eutrophication (e.g., Holmes
23 et al. 2000), the influence of the environment on bioerosion rates of the sponges is not so
24 evident (Holmes et al. 2009). The results from this study show that sponge bioerosion in *P.*
25 *astreoides* and *M. annularis* is lower in the suboptimal environmental conditions for reef-
26 building corals of the VRS when compared to MH. The results also indicate that sponge
27 bioerosion is higher in the denser skeletons of *P. astreoides* than in the less dense skeletons
28 of *M. annularis* in both localities (Table 1). These results support the idea that sponge
29 bioerosion is linked more to skeletal density than to environmental conditions.

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31 Finally, calcification is one of the most important processes occurring in coral reef
32 systems. Reef-building corals produce large amounts of calcium carbonate substratum,
33 which counters physical erosion of the reef structure (Wórum et al. 2007). Coral skeletal
34 density is a parameter constrained by a strictly defined upper limit (i.e., the density of
35 solid aragonitic CaCO₃), which is reduced by pores in the skeleton down to a minimal
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3 value caused presumably by mechanical or other constraints. It is expected that coral
4 calcification will be negatively affected with ocean warming and reduction on seawater
5 pH, due to elevated $p\text{CO}_2$ associated with climate change (e.g., Pandolfi et al. 2011;
6 Carricart-Ganivet et al. 2012). It is known that fast-growing coral species construct less-
7 dense skeletons (e.g., Hughes 1987) nonetheless when energetic resources favor increased
8 calcification *M. annularis* constructs denser skeletons, whereas *P. astreoides* uses the
9 extra resources to grow faster (Carricart-Ganivet 2004; Elizalde-Rendón et al. 2010).
10 Thus, any reduction in the calcification rate of *P. astreoides* may reduce its extension rate
11 and increase density (i.e., smaller pores in the skeleton), whereas reductions in
12 calcification in *M. annularis* would decrease its skeletal density. Thus, the effects of
13 climate change on sponge bioerosion rates could be different in the two species, with
14 uncertain repercussions on community structure in reef systems as well as for
15 biodiversity. Future work is needed to improve our understanding of the possible effects
16 of climate change on community structure in reef systems associated with sponge
17 bioerosion. For example, since boring sponges excrete acidic compounds, a reduction in
18 the seawater pH could make it less metabolically costly to lower the pH at the site of
19 erosion (Nava and Carballo 2008), making it easier to erode the coral skeleton and thus
20 promote bioerosion rates.
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37 **Acknowledgements** The manuscript was notably improved by the comments of A.
38 Banaszak (UASA, ICML, UNAM). We thank A.U. Beltrán-Torres (ECOSUR) and J.L.
39 Tello-Musi, and G. Horta-Puga (FESI, UNAM) for their assistance with field collections.
40 Special thanks to the staff of the “Parque Nacional Sistema Arrecifal Veracruzano”, for the
41 facilities provided during the fieldwork. During the investigation, L.M. Hernández-
42 Ballesteros was in the Postgraduates Program of ECOSUR and had a scholarship from
43 CONACYT. This research was supported by grants from CONACYT (projects U48757-F
44 and 102239), and CONABIO (project DM005).
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Figure legends

Fig. 1 Locations where corals were collected (stars)

Fig. 2 Percentage of total bioerosion by species and reef zone. Note that skeletal density increases from left to right (arrow). *Ma* = *Montastraea annularis*, *Pa* = *Porites astreoides*, VRS = Veracruz Reef System, MH = Mahahual. Error bars are standard error of the mean

Fig. 3 Percentage of total bioerosion as a function of skeletal density in several species of reef-building corals in several localities. Triangles are *Goniastrea retiformis*, *Porites lutea* and *Favia pallida* from Enewetak (Highsmith 1981b); squares are *Porites astreoides*, *Montastraea annularis* and *Montastraea cavernosa* from Belize (Highsmith et al. 1983); circles are *P. astreoides* and *M. faveolata* from the Veracruz Reef System and Mahahual (herein)

Fig. 4 Percentage of sponge bioerosion as a function of skeletal density in *Montastraea annularis* (squares; open = Veracruz Reef System, black = Mahahual) and *Porites astreoides* (circles; open = Veracruz Reef System, black = Mahahual). Error bars are standard error of the mean

Fig. 1 Locations where corals were collected (stars)
90x48mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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88x82mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 3 Percentage of total bioerosion as a function of skeletal density in several species of reef-building corals in several localities. Triangles are *Goniastrea retiformis*, *Porites lutea* and *Favia pallida* from Enewetak (Highsmith 1981b); squares are *Porites astreoides*, *Montastraea annularis* and *Montastraea cavernosa* from Belize (Highsmith et al. 1983); circles are *P. astreoides* and *M. faveolata* from the Veracruz Reef System and Mahahual (herein)
87x79mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 4 Percentage of sponge bioerosion as a function of skeletal density in *Montastraea annularis* (squares; open = Veracruz Reef System, black = Mahahual) and *Porites astreoides* (circles; open = Veracruz Reef System, black = Mahahual). Error bars are standard error of the mean
87x81mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Table 1 Mean skeletal density (g cm^{-3}) and bioerosion (%) caused by sponges, *Lithophaga*, sipunculans, non-identified organisms, as well as the total bioerosion in skeletons of *Montastraea annularis* (*Ma*), and *Porites astreoides* (*Pa*) growing in Mahahual (MH) and in the Veracruz Reef System (VRS). Standard deviations in parenthesis.

Species / Reef	Skeletal density	Bioerosion					Total
		Sponges	<i>Lithophaga</i>	Polychaetes	Sipunculans	Non-identified	
<i>Ma</i> / MH	1.40 (0.11)	3.60 (2.13)	0.16 (0.31)	0.00	0.02 (0.05)	0.03 (0.09)	3.81 (2.24)
<i>Ma</i> / VRS	1.32 (0.16)	1.34 (2.66)	0.21 (0.59)	0.04 (0.10)	0.05 (0.16)	0.05 ((0.18)	1.70 (3.41)
<i>Pa</i> / MH	1.60 (0.18)	6.69 (4.95)	0.30 (0.65)	0.04 (0.10)	0.42 (0.53)	0.00	7.45 (4.50)
<i>Pa</i> / VRS	1.38 (0.12)	2.74 (2.27)	0.21 (0.41)	0.73 (1.77)	0.04 (0.11)	0.00	3.72 (3.14)

Table 2 Contribution (%) of sponges, *Lithophaga*, polychaetes and sipunculans to total bioerosion in skeletons of *Montastraea annularis* (*Ma*), and *Porites astreoides* (*Pa*) growing in Mahahual (MH) and in the Veracruz Reef System (VRS).

Species / Reef	Sponges	<i>Lithophaga</i>	Polychaetes	Sipunculans
<i>Ma</i> / MH	94.49	4.20	0.00	0.52
<i>Ma</i> / VRS	78.82	12.35	2.35	2.94
<i>Pa</i> / MH	89.80	4.03	0.54	5.64
<i>Pa</i> / VRS	73.66	5.65	19.62	1.08

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